

**APPLICATION OF THE SYLLABLE READING METHOD
FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' READING ABILITY IN
LEARNING INDONESIAN LANGUAGE IN CLASS I
STATE STATE 35 PRIVATE SCHOOL 35 TRANS SATA
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Abstract: This research was carried out because in the delivery of material by the teacher, students did not understand it. This has an impact on students' low reading abilities, resulting in low student learning outcomes. This is because the delivery of the material is not supported by appropriate learning media, inappropriate supporting books, and inappropriate methods. This research is one of the graduation requirements for the PKP course and increases the teacher's ability to design learning using the syllabic reading method, with the aim of increasing students' reading ability and understanding of material as well as increasing the trust of the community around the school. The focus of this research lies in students' reading abilities using the syllabic reading method. Research activities are divided into two cycles with each cycle consisting of one face-to-face meeting. It is hoped that the results of this research can improve students' reading ability and student learning outcomes according to the established Kkm. From the achievement of the results of the student learning process using the syllabic reading method, there has been an increase. This can be seen from cycle one with an average class score of 58 to 84 in cycle two and a percentage of 30% in cycle one to 90% in cycle two.

Keywords: Reading ability, Elementary School Indonesian Language Learning, and Syllable Reading Method.

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Introduction

Management of improving the quality of education in schools is a method of improving quality that is based on education in the school itself, applying a set of techniques, based on the availability of quantitative and qualitative data, and empowering all school components to continuously increase the capacity and ability of the school organization to meet the needs of students and society (Azmi & Ridho, 2019).

According to Ratih Mustikawati (2015:43) that "Reading ability is one of the keys to student success in achieving progress. With adequate ability, students will find it easier to dig up information from various written sources." So beginning reading is very important initial learning for the lower classes as a basic material for achieving further knowledge. According to Mustikawati (2015:46) the

syllable method is a method that begins with the introduction of syllables and is sequenced into meaningful words. In this method, children do not need to know the letters one by one, but will be introduced to syllables. The syllable method can make it easier for students to learn to read at the beginning of class I.

After observing the results of class I student learning carried out at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-mata, only 3 out of 10 class I students had the ability to read, the students did not understand the delivery of the material presented, the books used for reading lessons and the use of the methods used. less precise.

The method of reading syllables was deliberately chosen by the author because according to Riduan M (2018:10) he said that there are 5 advantages in the method of reading syllables, namely : (1) it can be taught directly even without going through seminars/workshops; (2) children read directly without having to know letters; (3) the child's concentration is not broken. Children are able to identify words accurately and correctly even if they are turned upside down; (4) children do not know the memorization method; and (5) children's abilities are measured mathematically and systematically.

From the data that has been obtained, researchers are looking for solutions so that students can improve their reading skills and can create an active and meaningful learning atmosphere in learning so that the results they want to achieve are in accordance with the objectives, namely achieving reading skills and in accordance with KKM standards. Of the various learning methods that researchers have explored, the syllable reading method is the right method to overcome problems related to students' reading abilities and the use of a supporting book entitled "Learning to Read the MSK Method" by Riduan M, makes it easier for researchers to convey the material and makes it easier for students to understand. at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata Mata, North Kayong District

Based on this, a formulation of the problem faced by researchers was obtained, including : (1) How to plan the initial reading learning process in learning Indonesian using the syllabic reading method for students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata? (2) Can the reading ability of class I students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata in Indonesian language subjects improve through the syllabic reading method ? (3) Can using the syllable reading method create an active and meaningful learning atmosphere for class I students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata in the Indonesian language subject?

The objectives to be achieved from this research include: (1) to find out the extent of success in planning the initial reading learning process in learning Indonesian using the syllabic reading method for students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata (2) to improve reading skills students after using the syllable reading method (3) to create an active and meaningful learning atmosphere for class I students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata in the Indonesian language subject using the syllable reading method and (4) as a requirement for passing the Ability Strengthening course Professional (PKP) PDGK 4501 PGSD Bachelor Program and to achieve a Bachelor's degree in Elementary School Education.

It is hoped that from this research the benefits obtained include: (a) for researchers to be able to find out the advantages and disadvantages in carrying out the reading learning process in the

Indonesian language subject for class I students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata, using the syllabic reading method (b) for students can find out the level of student success after carrying out the process of learning to read in the Indonesian language subject for class I students at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata, using the syllable reading method and (c) for schools it can be useful for increasing the achievement of reading skills and in accordance with student KKM standards, especially in Indonesian language subjects, as well as increasing the trust of the community around the school concerned..

Methods

The subjects of this research were 10 class I students at SD Negeri 35 Mata-Mata, consisting of 6 male students and 4 female students, with the reason that only 3 of the 10 class I students had the ability to read and lacked understanding. students will understand the material presented. This research was carried out at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata Mata, North Kayong District. The research was carried out on Thursday 2 May 2024 for cycle I and Saturday 11 May 2024 for cycle II. The parties involved in the research were Mr. Sukino, S.Pd, I as supervisor I and the head of SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-Mata, North Kayong District and Mrs. Susilawani, S.Pd as supervisor II.

The design of learning improvement procedures is (1) this research uses a Classroom Action Research design. In simple terms, Classroom Action Research can be defined as a process of controlled investigation that is recyclable and self-reflective in nature carried out by teachers/prospective teachers with the aim of making improvements to systems, ways of working, processes, content, competencies or learning situations. Another definition states that action research is research about, for and by society by utilizing interaction, participation and collaboration between researchers and target groups. Apart from that, Classroom Action Research is also defined as a problem solving strategy that utilizes real actions and a process of developing capabilities in detecting and resolving problems. In the process, the parties involved support each other by providing facts and developing analytical skills. In practice, Classroom Action Research combines meaningful action with research procedures.

This is an effort to solve the problem while seeking scientific support. Consciously, the parties involved (teacher candidates, teachers, lecturers, lecturers, instructors, school principals and community members) try to formulate an action or intervention that is calculated to solve the problem or improve the situation and are expected to carefully observe its implementation to understand the level of success. Classroom Action Research is reflective research carried out in cycles by teachers/prospective teachers in the classroom. It is said that because the Classroom Action Research process starts from the stages of planning, action, observation and reflection to solve problems and try new things to improve the quality of learning; (2) the objectives of Classroom Action Research are (a) Classroom Action Research is carried out for the sake of improving and/or increasing learning practices on an ongoing basis which is basically attached to the implementation of the teacher's professional educational mission. Therefore, Classroom Action Research is a strategic way to improve and enhance educational services that must be carried out in a context. Apart from that, it is also to improve the overall quality of school programs in a rapidly changing society.

The main aim of Classroom Action Research is to improve and enhance teachers' professional services in handling PBM which can be achieved by reflecting to diagnose the situation. Reflecting is carrying out analysis-synthesis-interpretation-explanation and drawing conclusions, then testing alternative actions and evaluating their effectiveness. This series of activities constitutes a cycle of action; (b) the aim of Classroom Action Research is to develop teacher skills to deal with actual learning problems in their class and/or at their own school; (c) the aim of accompanying Classroom Action Research is to foster a research culture among Classroom Action Research teachers and lecturers as educators (Depdikbud, 1999: 10); (d) the aim of Classroom Action Research is to improve and increase the quality of teaching (learning) through appropriate teaching techniques according to the problems and level of development of students.

Classroom Action Research is also intended as a way to empower teachers and improve teachers' abilities in making the right decisions for students and the classes they teach; (3) the various benefits obtained from Classroom Action Research provide great hope for solving learning problems in the classroom, namely as follows: (a) teachers and prospective teachers can immediately improve learning practices so that they become better and more effective; (b) teachers and prospective teachers can research their own practical learning activities in class; (c) teachers and prospective teachers can see, feel and appreciate whether the learning practices carried out so far are highly effective; (d) teachers and prospective teachers can look for new ways/procedures to improve and increase teacher professionalism in PBM in the classroom by looking at various indicators of the success of the learning process and outcomes that occur with students; (e) fostering a research culture in teachers/teacher candidates so that learning innovation occurs (Depdikbud, 1999; 15); (f) increasing the professionalism of teachers/teacher candidates, especially the ability to describe the curriculum in accordance with local, school and class demands; (g) improve the quality of teaching and student learning outcomes based on direct findings from the teacher's own class; (h) develop cooperation or collaboration between teachers at that school and teachers at other schools in solving teaching and learning problems; (i) fostering the habit of teachers/prospective teachers implementing research-oriented learning (learning through research) and (j) familiarizing teachers/other parties with solving problems and formulating learning programs based on contextual empirical findings (Wardani, et al, 2003: 1.20); (4) This research was planned in two cycles.

Cycle I aims to determine the extent of students' reading abilities and also as an initial research action, as well as being used as reflection material for carrying out cycle II. Cycle II aims to determine the improvement in students' reading abilities after improvements have been made to the implementation of the teaching and learning process based on cycle I reflection; and (5) Kurt Lewin's Classroom Action Research design model is the main reference or basis for various other action research models, especially Classroom Action Research because he was the first to introduce Action Research or action research. The main concept of action research in the Kurt Lewin Model consists of four components, namely a) planning, b) acting, c) observing, and d) reflecting. The minimum completion criteria for class I Indonesian at SD Negeri 35 Trans Mata-mata is 65.

Results and Discussion

CYCLE I

Planning

At the planning stage of cycle I, several preparations were made. Preparations made include: (a) making a learning implementation plan; (b) preparation of test instruments that will be tested in the formative test; (c) preparation of assessment guidelines to assess tests on students' reading abilities using syllabic reading methods orally and in writing and (d) preparation of non-test instruments in the form of observation guidelines.

Action

Action is an application of the learning implementation plan. At this stage: (a) the researcher attempts to take action in accordance with what was planned at the planning stage and (b) the teacher acts as an instructor who presents material and guides students in learning.

Observation

The observations made by the researcher are related to: (a) all student learning activities that occur during the learning process regarding students' reading abilities using oral and written syllabic reading methods, and (b) the author must be able to record what happens during the learning process using guided by the observation sheet that had been prepared previously. The results of this observation are data that will become material for reflection for researchers.

Reflection

The reflection stage is carried out with the aim of: (a) finding out what has happened after the learning process about learning to read using the syllabic reading method; (b) the researcher analyzed the test and non-test results of cycle I. The author not only analyzed, but then tried to determine whether the actions taken were effective and what things needed to be improved so that they could be made effective again in cycle II; and (c) the problems that arise in cycle I will be resolved in cycle II, while the advantages will be maintained and improved.

CYCLE II

Planning

Things to do include making plans for implementing learning improvements and recording problems and obstacles faced during learning in cycle I.

Action

Action is an application of the learning implementation plan. At this stage the researcher carried out an analysis to solve the problems that occurred in cycle I and took corrective action.

Observation

The observations that the researcher made were related to all student learning activities that occurred during the learning improvement process regarding the application of the syllabic reading method and the researcher must be able to record all changes that occurred.

Reflection

As a researcher, reflect again on the progress of learning improvement in cycle II. From the evaluation results, it can be seen that almost all weaknesses and failures have been resolved, and many changes have even undergone.

Every time you make improvements to learning, researchers will create a learning design that is based on learning outcomes. After creating a design, the researcher implements the design, supervisor II provides input on findings or failures and lessons learned in both cycle I and cycle II.

The advantages found in cycle I include (1) application of the correct method for reading syllables; (2) learning support books are appropriate; (3) students' learning outcomes improve; and (4) implementation of the learning process in an orderly manner. The shortcomings include: (1) not all students understand the explanation given by the teacher; (2) learning media that is not yet varied; (3) there are still student scores that have not reached the kkm; and (4) the time allocation is felt to be insufficient.

Cycle II, the evaluation results achieved by the students were satisfactory because almost all students achieved learning completeness, namely 9 of the 10 students who reached the kkm and 1 person who did not reach the kkm. Based on the results of this evaluation, supervisor II, a researcher who is also a teacher and supervisor I who also acts as the school principal agreed to make a decision that in cycle II this had achieved the expected goals. For this reason, it can be concluded that there is no further improvement.

According to Sabarti Akharga (2001/2002 3135) "explains that the syllable method is the application of letter recognition to students, namely combining syllables into letters and finally into words". This means that reading is a combination of activities such as recognizing letters and words, connecting them with their sounds and meanings, and drawing conclusions about the meaning of the answer.

According to Supriyadi (2002: 12) the Syllable Method is a method that begins teaching reading by presenting more meaningful words. This means that reading is a unified activity such as an approach with stories accompanied by pictures in it which are useful for recognizing letters. and words.

According to Hairuddin (2002 61-62) the Syllable Method is "a method that begins with the introduction of syllables and is arranged into meaningful words or some people call it the Word Method or Institutional Words". This means putting together words that have been put together into simple sentences.

Reading is one of the aspects of language skills that every student, especially a student, must have. The four skills are speaking, reading, listening and writing. If a person does a lot of reading

activities, he will automatically increase his vocabulary, increase his knowledge, train his speech tools, train his reasoning power, and will also be able to respond to the content of the reading. Farr states that Reading Is The Heart Of Education, which means that reading is the heart of education (Puspitasari , 2015).

Reading has an important role apart from getting information and can also broaden the reader's insight. According to Pramila and Ahuja, if you have the ability to read well, you have achieved the most valuable skill in your life. Another opinion from Burn regarding the importance of skills and abilities in every person is that the ability to read is an absolute ability and must be mastered by a more advanced society. Reading also has an important role in teaching and learning activities at school. Reading is not only used in Indonesian language learning subjects but for all subjects because most of the acquisition of knowledge is carried out by students through reading activities.

According to Cicilia and Nursalim, reading has the aim of finding information in a reading text, both explicit (facts) and implied (inference) information (Cicilia & Nursalim. 2019). In the 2003 National Education System Law, Chapter III, article 4, paragraph 5, which discusses the Principles of Implementing Education, it is stated that the importance of learning to read is for all members of society. It can be concluded that every human being must have the skills and ability to read because by reading humans can obtain the knowledge and information needed for a smooth life.

Students' success in participating in learning and increasing their knowledge is greatly influenced by their reading ability. Therefore, teaching reading has a very important strategic position in the learning process. However, not all people and society are aware of this, so reading has not yet become a basic and basic need. According to Iskandarwassid and Dadang Sunendar, reading skills are acquired and learned at school (Maulana, et al, 2017).

In this regard, students can grow, develop and improve reading skills through teaching and learning activities (KBM) at school. The more skilled a person is at understanding reading, the clearer and more open their thoughts will be. In learning to read, children must understand the relationship between reading and the content of the reading. Teaching reading must provide understanding to children that when reading they must also produce understanding.

Reading comprehension is an activity where someone understands the content of the reading, and is limited to questions about what , why, how, and drawing conclusions based on what is read. The ability of understanding that a person has is not an ability that is passed down from generation to generation, but is the result of a learning process and diligent practice. Reading comprehension is a reading activity carried out to capture in-depth main ideas so that the reader has satisfaction after reading (in Rahayu, 2012). According to Kusman, reading comprehension skills are reading activities carried out carefully and thoroughly by readers to hone critical reading skills with the aim of understanding reading in detail (Prihatsanti et 2018).

Conclusion

From the entire series of learning processes and research that have been carried out, the following conclusions can be obtained : (1) improving teacher performance and professionalism in

designing and implementing a learning process, namely learning to read using the syllabic reading method; (2) using the syllabic reading method in learning can improve students' reading abilities. This can be seen from the increase in the average value of each cycle, from 58 in cycle I to 84 in cycle II. Increase in the percentage of completion value for each cycle, from 30% in cycle I to 90% in cycle II; and (3) learning using the syllabic reading method can create an active learning process, this can be seen from the interactions that occur between students and students and between students and teachers, thereby creating meaningful learning.

It is recommended for fellow teachers to use the syllabic reading method as a first step in teaching students to read at the beginning, especially for grade 1 elementary school students in learning Indonesian, because the use of this method can lead students to construct their own knowledge, thereby creating an active learning situation. and meaningful. As teachers we must be smart in choosing appropriate methods in learning. To school principals to provide opportunities for teachers to be creative in carrying out the teaching and learning process.

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